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Medieval Irish Law as Alternative Justice in Nineteenth- and Twentieth-Century Ireland

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Abstract: The mid-nineteenth-century project to translate the corpus of medieval Irish law brought a specialist subject area into the public domain. The publication of the legal tracts across the second half of the nineteenth century, not only highlighted the vast amount of medieval Irish legal material, but served also as a rallying point for Irish Nationalists, who saw another way to shake off the British yoke. This article examines the presentation of the laws as an alternative legal space separate from English law in the nineteenth century; how medieval Irish law was considered as a replacement legal system in an imagined independent Ireland to serve justice in a more Irish way; and, in an independent Ireland, as a means to justice when denied by official channels.

Keywords: Early Irish Law, Antiquarianism, Nineteenth-Century Ireland, Politics, Translation

In 1852 two antiquarians and clergymen, James Henthorn Todd and Charles Graves, petitioned the British Government for funding to translate the corpus of medieval Irish law, commonly referred to as Brehon law.¹ In *The Report of the Commissioners appointed to Inquire and Report concerning the Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland*, which had been submitted to Parliament in early 1852, the two gentlemen highlighted that the publication of the law tracts in translation might have a particular interest for politicians. They wrote that:

There are some circumstances which would render the publication of these ancient laws peculiarly interesting in the eyes of the politician. It is not improbable that the habits of thought and action prevailing amongst the native Irish are reflected in the laws which they framed for themselves before they were affected by foreign influences, and to which they continued to cling with obstinate tenacity, even for centuries after they had been compelled to submit to British rule. The Brehon Laws were actually appealed to so late as the reign of Charles I. We must not, therefore, be surprised to find some traces yet remaining of their effect upon society. We would also suggest that good results would be obtained by exhibiting the real state of this country at a remote period of its history. It would then be found that false or exaggerated notions have been entertained of the well-being of society and the advancement of civilisation in early times. Ireland never enjoyed a golden age. It would be more true to say, that she suffered for many ages under an iron feudalism, which administered essentially different laws to the rich and to the poor. Ignorance on this head has certainly created in some minds an unreasonable dissatisfaction with the present order of things, and a perverse disposition to thwart the efforts of those who are doing their utmost to ameliorate it. Nothing could be more efficacious in dispelling such morbid national prejudices than a complete publication of the ancient Irish laws.²

The emphasis on a lack of Irish golden age and the reference to political interest serve to demonstrate that, although the publication of the laws could be used for political purposes, the content of the publication would soon show that the early medieval Irish past could not be weaponised in such a way as to cause disturbance. This was certainly the fear of some Members of Parliament, as is shown in a speech in the House of Lords in June 1852, in which Lord Monteaigle stated that:

He was aware that on the part of some who, to him, appeared not only prejudiced but shallow reasoners, there was felt some apprehension that the publication of these ancient records might stimulate national feelings of restlessness and discontent. He did not participate in what he considered so weak and irrational an alarm. But on this subject he should take the liberty of reading an extract from the Report itself, which would serve to remove these

fears, wherever they might be found to exist. For himself he needed not any confirmation of what he considered an undeniable principle, namely, that the publication and diffusion of truth could not be other than useful in all cases, and without any exception.³

Even before any work had begun on transcribing and translating the corpus of medieval Irish law, there were fears that the project would provide those who could seek to undermine British rule in Ireland with the means to do so. The two extracts above demonstrate the potential power that even the concept of a corpus of law pre-dating English Common Law had in challenging established authority and how it was necessary to allay those fears by downplaying the result of the project – that Ireland had a fully functioning code of law before the Cambrian Norman invasion in the twelfth century.⁴ Yet, despite assurances from the Commissioners and certain Members of Parliament supportive of the endeavour that the result of the project would be solely philological, the production of the *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland* over the second-half of the nineteenth century did cause some to consider their past uses and how they might serve in such a way to again. This article examines how early Irish law was considered to serve as an alternative legal space in nineteenth- and twentieth-century Ireland when justice could not be obtained through more official channels.

The Translation of the Laws

Long before the project to transcribe and translate the laws was begun and the Commission to superintend this project appointed, the concept of early Irish law was known of and was seen as a source of pride. There had been previous attempts to translate the laws by earlier scholars such as Charles Vallancey, but the difficulty of the texts made this an arduous undertaking which required scholars with the necessary linguistic skills and training to be able to do this. The laws are written in a deliberately difficult language, commonly referred to as 'dark speech', as the 'Pseudo-Historical Prologue' to the *Senchas Már* refers to it: *Ba dorcha didiu in labra ro labrasatar ind filid isin fuigiull-sin* (Dark was the speech which the poets spoke in that case).⁵ However, in the mid-nineteenth century, the scholars John O'Donovan and Eugene O'Curry had proven themselves to be able

scholars, who would be capable of taking on this project. Once their work for the Topographical Department of the Ordnance Survey of Ireland came to a close in 1842, the two scholars were employed separately on various projects to catalogue manuscripts in Irish in Trinity College Dublin. While undertaking this task, the idea of translating the legal tracts they dealt with was raised and was well received by several antiquarians. Plans were begun in 1843 to begin translating the corpus of early Irish law, as is evidenced by the transactions of the Irish Archaeological Society, prefixed to John O'Donovan's edition and translation of *The Tribes and Customs of Hy-Many* for that Society. A point of the agenda refers to O'Donovan's work on *Cormac's Glossary* before discussing future works, such as 'the difficult and laborious work of editing our ancient Brehon Laws, Annals, &c.'. This also includes discovering what other legal material and glossaries on the subject remained in other repositories outside of Ireland and in private hands.⁶ Charles Graves had always had O'Donovan and O'Curry in mind to undertake the transcription and translation, as his letter to O'Donovan in 1851, before funding had been acquired, demonstrates. He wrote:

As the work of publishing the Brehon laws is the most important that Irish scholars could be engaged in, the duty of reporting on them ought to be performed with the greatest care and diligence.

It was with a view to this that I made representations to the Government which led to their placing at the disposal of Dr Todd and myself the sum of £200 to be spent in procuring necessary assistance – I saw that it was essential that you and Curry should be employed in preparing a catalogue of the MSS of the Irish Laws; and generally in collecting materials for the Report.⁷

O'Curry worked at a translation of a portion of the *Book of Acaill*, which was submitted with the aforementioned *Report* and request for funding to the British Government, who provided £5,000 to begin the project and £500 per annum afterwards to create and maintain a commission to superintend the work.⁸ It was originally envisaged that the work of transcribing and translating would take several years,⁹ though this was not to be the case due to a series of events. O'Donovan and O'Curry, who had been appointed joint-editors in 1853, were replaced in 1860 by W. Neilson Hancock and his assistant Thomas Busteed, due to their purportedly indifferent command of

English and legal archaeology.¹⁰ John O'Donovan died in 1861 and Eugene O'Curry in 1862 long before their work went to print. Volume I was published in 1865, Volume II in 1869, III in 1873, IV in 1879, and V, along with VI – a glossary – were published in 1901.

As was evident from the long publication history, the task before the translators was enormous. It was likely not known then that the legal corpus is the largest vernacular collection in Western Europe both in terms of size and variety,¹¹ though Eugene O'Curry remarked in his *Lectures on the Manuscript Materials of Ancient Irish History* that 'this collection is so immense in extent and the subjects dealt with throughout the whole of it, in the utmost detail, are so numerous [...]'.¹² Another source of pride was the purported antiquity of the laws. A text known as the 'Pseudo-Historical Prologue' to the compendium of legal tracts known as the *Senchas Már* makes reference to the judgement of St Patrick upon the Christian nature of the laws and their re-working to make them acceptable to him. John Carey has dated this text linguistically and by reference to the *Bretha Nemed* law texts to around the late-eighth or ninth century,¹³ which is, of course, much later than traditional mid-fifth century date ascribed to Patrick. The 'Preface' to Volume I of *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland*, which covers the *Senchas Már*, makes explicit reference to this tradition of Patrick sanitising the laws to be in line with Christian teaching, making reference to the antiquity of the laws.¹⁴ The antiquity of the laws was referenced in the appeal for funding submitted to the Government as being both of interest to the philologist and to the historian. In a more general audience this was portrayed as something about which to be proud. A journal article in 1871 spoke about the long history of the law texts in a very romantic and proud way, especially when compared with England:

Dating from a period with the mists of traditional antiquity, and stretching far beyond the horizon of established history, when their Scythic ancestors crossed in tribes the plains or poured through the passes of Northern Germany, this system of government had certainly existed in Ireland for upwards of 1,600 years. Guided by laws simple in principle but complex in detail, patriarchal in authority but absolute in practice, mild in regulation but sternly opposed to progress and antagonistic to individual liberty, the system had a wonderful vitality on Irish soil. Within six centuries England had thrice changed her language and her laws

and twice her religion. But no corresponding changes in that period had occurred in Ireland. There the people spoke in the same tongue and worshipped at the same altars that their forefathers had spoken in and knelt at for ages back. Outside the Pale the Brehon was as implicitly obeyed in the fifteenth as he had been in the fifth century.¹⁵

The fact that the laws were still appealed to in the early modern era was also mentioned in the appeal and in the 'Preface', and it is this long postmedieval afterlife which allowed early Irish law to be imagined as a form of alternative legal space in later periods, particularly as it came to be viewed as 'native' in opposition to 'foreign' legal systems.

Alternative Legal Space in Post-Medieval Ireland

The five waves of the Cambro-Norman invasion in the 1160s and 1170s had very little change on the way law was conducted in Ireland.¹⁶ Outside of the Pale, the hereditary learned families continued practising their craft and being patronised by the families they served. This included the families of legal experts. Accounts from English officials in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries illuminate how the practice of law, as laid out in the early medieval law tracts, had changed little over the following centuries. One account from the sixteenth century portrays the Brehon as an idle, greedy figure, which it would be better for the Colonists to do without:

The fourste of them is called the Brehounde, whiche in English is called the judge; and before they will geave judgement they will have pawnes of both the parties, the which is called in Irish, Ulliege; and then they will geave judgement according to their own dischresions. Theis men be neuters, and the Irishmen will not prate them; they have great pleantie of cattell, and they harbour manye vacabons and ydell parsons, and if their be anye rebell that moves anye rebellion against the prince, of theis people they ar chiffe mantayned; and if the English armye fortune to travell in that parties wher they be, they will fle into mountains and woodes, bycause they wold not sucker them with vitals and other; — and further, they will take upon them to judge matters and redresse causes, as well of inherytans as of other matters, although they are ignoraunt; the which is a greater

hinderans to the Quenes Majestie's laws, and hurtfull to the whole English Pale.¹⁷

Despite this portrayal of the Brehon and the law they practised as a 'hinderans to the Quenes Majestie's laws', Irish law was not completely subsumed by English law during this period. As Gearóid Mac Niocaill has argued, due to the expansion of the MacEgan family of lawyers into 'theoretically Anglo-Norman areas', such as Ormond and Clanrickard, this led to the Earls of Ormond and Kildare, and their ilk, to become 'legally ambidextrous'. As Mac Niocaill describes, this meant they employed Irish or common law as the 'circumstances dictated'.¹⁸ Herbert Francis Hore and James Graves, citing David Sutton's 'Presentment', give the example of the Earl of Kildare in 1534 using both the 'prince's laws and the brehens laws, which he thought most beneficial as the case did require'.¹⁹ This had clearly become such an issue that, earlier, in 1519, the by-laws for the town of Galway — an 'ancient colonie of English'²⁰ — stated that 'that no Irish judge or lawire shall plede in no man's cause or matter within this town or courte, for it agreth not with the king's laws'.²¹ Even though there was a preference in certain circles for common law, Irish law was still something which could provide justice when it suited those applying it. A sense of fairness and justice is prevalent when Irish law is discussed: James Hardiman footnotes the entry in his *History* by saying that:

the native Irish (whose love of strict and impartial justice was celebrated even by their enemies) neither acknowledged nor obeyed any other than the Brehon laws, to the reign of James I. Until then the English laws were in force only within the Pale, which consisted of the counties of Dublin, Kildare, Meath and Louth, and within the cities of Dublin, Cork, Waterford, Limerick, Galway, and a few other places.²²

Comments like this emphasised that Irish law, as it had been transmitted and adapted from the medieval period was inherently more Irish and had a legal currency in areas outside of the Pale. Even later in time, we see commentators linking the continuation of medieval legal practices to contemporaneous ones. One example, published just after the Brehon Law project had just begun, was the linking of gavelkind, as it was practiced in the mid-nineteenth century,

with its medieval precedents, to demonstrate the relevance that the earlier laws had on the present day.²³ Gavelkind was the division of land among all sons, not just the eldest. In early Irish law, this included sons from outside of marriage, as long as they were recognised by the wife and there was no chance of doubt being cast on the paternity of the child.²⁴ A special ruling by Irish judges in 1606 removed gavelkind in Gaelic districts, yet the Act for Preventing the Further Growth of Popery (1704) abolished primogeniture for Catholics who refused to conform, effectively reinstating gavelkind on Catholic landowners.²⁵ If the eldest son converted, he inherited the whole. This law was repealed in 1778 with the first substantial relaxation of the penal laws.²⁶ When Hore came to write this article in 1857, the repeal of this law was in living memory of some Catholic landowners, however Hore does not mention the punitive reasons for the restitution of this legal matter. Hore ascribes the continued practice of gavelkind to 'the desire for general equality'.²⁷

In matters pertaining to land division and agrarian practices, there was often an idea about an alternative system of justice in nineteenth-century Ireland. As Heather Laird highlights, in rural areas there were often alternative legal spaces with systems of law and punishments of transgressions that were separate from official legal processes. She gives the examples of boycotting, alternative courts and tribunals held by various associations such as the Ribbonmen and the Land League, and various other unwritten codes of law.²⁸ As she points out, particularly when it relates to land, was that there were alternative legal spaces, or, as she puts it: 'a space outside of official law'.²⁹ She bases her views on the work of two British commentators in Ireland during the nineteenth century, who both independently came to the conclusion that 'English law may be the only law that receives official recognition in Ireland, but this does not mean that alternative concepts of legality do not exist'.³⁰ Campbell saw the official rejection of Irish law and the lack of incorporation of it into an Irish context as the original of oppositional law in Ireland.³¹ Laird, remarking upon Campbell and Gibbs, along with several other modern commentators, concludes that, while this alternative legal system in Ireland was unlikely to be a direct continuation of early Irish law, it still fulfilled the function of a legal system that Irish law had once inhabited.³² Even if early Irish law had no legal recourse in the nineteenth century, it proved, nevertheless, to be an attractive concept.

The Attraction of Medieval Irish Law in the Nineteenth and Twentieth Centuries

Even if alternative law in Ireland was not a direct descendent of medieval Irish law, there was still a tie in many people's minds between it and 'Brehon' law. This was partly due to the promotion of the *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland* as highlighting practices of ancient laws still evident in Ireland, as we have seen already above in the extract from the funding application. It was also due to this idea of medieval Irish law as providing an alternative means to justice when it was denied by more official means. As Hore wrote in his 1857 article, the idea of Brehon law was based on 'a desire for general equality'.³³ Hore also highlighted in this piece what many commentators have emphasised and promoted, even before the project to translate the corpus of medieval Irish law was announced – that Irish law was considered to be based upon restorative justice, rather than punitive, writing that 'the admirable leniency of its penal provisions, has turned the balance of opinion in its favour on this important score. Many offences which the Draconian English code visited with loss of life or liberty were under it chastised more mercifully by fines'.³⁴ This view of a fairer system of governance, along with ideas such as the communal ownership of land, as described in numerous publications,³⁵ meant that to many inhabitants of nineteenth-century Ireland suffering hard lives post-Famine, it was an extremely attractive concept. Even in the 1930s this idea was still in place; among communities in summer animal grazing pastures there was a *breitheamh* or judge who would reapportion land to ensure all the tenants had fair share of the mountain grazing, which they had been denied under the official rundale scheme.³⁶ Such ideas could be developed even further by modern commentators, who took the publication of the law texts in English and used them to suit their own aims and agendas. One example is the Socialist and Irish Nationalist James Connolly, who used the idea of shared land ownership portrayed in the medieval law texts to argue that medieval Ireland had been a Socialist utopia and that these conditions should be reinstated in a future independent Ireland.³⁷ The idea of a return to the superior old ways was an idea which was touted by many a Nationalist in the late-nineteenth and early-twentieth centuries. Another example of this was the Secretary of the Dublin (Workers)

Towns Tenants League, William J. Larkin, who in 1922, during the so-called 'Galway Soviet' in which the statue of Lord Dunkellin was thrown into Galway Bay, stood in Eyre Square in that city and, repeating Connolly's words, cried out for the return of 'Brehon Law', stating that:

Who made the laws under which you live at the present time? The thieves of the country. Who robbed you of every right you ever possessed, and continues to do it today? What law are you under? [...] Why are we not under the Brehon Code if we have an Irish government? Is it because there are too many clauses in that code which are favourable to the tenantry?³⁸

Aside from Larkin's comments that 'Brehon' law was more suitable to be an Irish law code than English law as it was more sympathetic to the tenant, and therefore, to the Irish people more widely, he was also aiding Connolly's argument that socialism was not incompatible with life in Ireland. As John Cunningham states, Connolly used early Irish law to counteract claims that socialism was a foreign import and instead argued that in its nature, early medieval Irish society was socialist and that capitalism had been imported with the English invasion in the twelfth century. Cunningham points out that Connolly had not been advocating for the re-instatement of early Irish law itself.³⁹ The Nationalist Teachta Dála, Laurence Ginnell, also did not advocate for the reintroduction of the early laws, but felt that they should be of great influence in helping develop an Irish legal code in a future independent Ireland. He argued in his lectures on the early laws, published as *The Brehon Laws: A Legal Handbook*, that the laws were uniquely Irish and had no trace of Roman law evident in them.⁴⁰ While, since Ginnell published his work, it has been clearly demonstrated that Canon law had a great influence on the laws,⁴¹ this view was a popular one and had been since the project to translate the laws was announced. Ginnell's interest was as a legal historian but he saw some merit in the laws that should make other lawyers want to study the laws themselves for potential uses. In a third edition of the text, published posthumously after his death in 1923, the editor of this used his preface to argue for the early laws to form the basis of a new law code, as they were something uniquely Irish. James Kerr, the editor in question, argued that 'why should there not be a

distinctive legal system based on purely Irish legal principles?'.⁴² He went on to argue for a chair in this subject, claiming that:

The Language Movement alone will not satisfy the new spirit of Irish Freedom. The movement towards a distinctly Irish Legal System must proceed alongside of it. Education in this work of Legal Reconstruction must be made Irish. Not a score of present-day Irish lawyers know an iota of Irish Law. They only know English Law. This is where Mr. Ginnell's book will now, after thirty years' waiting, come at length into its own. Irish Professors of Jurisprudence have up till now been content that Irish students should get their knowledge of ancient Irish Law solely from the lectures of an English Oxford Don, Sir Henry Sumner Maine. That will have to be changed. Some of these Professors claim to be Irish patriots. Here is a test for their patriotism.⁴³

Possibly inspired by Kerr's sentiments or even by the inspiration of the production of Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland, there was discussion of a Chair in Brehon Laws to be held at University College, Dublin. A newspaper report in 1932 lists three names who are suspected to be awarded it (John MacNeill, R. A. S. MacAlister, and Daniel Binchy), as well as suggesting that students studying Celtic at the university will be offered lectures in the subject of Brehon law.⁴⁴

Medieval Irish Law as Alternative Justice

University College Dublin never did institute a Chair of Brehon Law, but two of the named persons who could have been offered the post did have use to employ medieval Irish law in the courtroom. In the 1920s, 1930s, and 1940s, a series of court cases between the Erne Fishing Company and six men accused of poaching salmon used early Irish law in the court room to defend the accused.⁴⁵ Medieval law was first cited in the case in 1925 when the lawyer for the defence claimed that, according to the Magna Carta, that private fisheries could not be created on tidal waters after the death of Henry II in 1189. As the Erne Fishery Company dated from the 1920s and was based upon a portion of the estuary that had been owned by the planter Thomas Ffolliott since 1639, the lawyer argued that it could not be privately owned and, therefore, the men were not poaching. After Eoin Mac Néill (the aforementioned John MacNeill) stated that private fisheries

were unknown in Gaelic Ireland, the defence decided to invoke early Irish law in its proceedings.⁴⁶ This was also due to the fact that the defence had to prove that exclusive fishing rights did not exist before 1189.⁴⁷ Mac Néill and Daniel Bichy began supplying the defence with evidence that such rights were foreign to early Irish law and that this legal system was still in place in Donegal until the seventeenth century.⁴⁸ As a historian of early medieval Ireland, Mac Néill outlined for the court the rights of a member of a *túath* and cited the following extract from the law tract *Do Fastad Chirt 7 Dilgid* ('On the confirmation of right and law'):

How many things have been established as the inherent rights of every territory and which are equally due to every person? The salmon of every place; wild garlic; the *andach* property of each water; the quick drawing [of a net] from each stream; the sufficiency for a night of faggots of each wood which has not the tripartite division of [trees]; cooking-fuel in each wood; the mat [nuts] of each wood; materials for each carriage; timber for body-bearers; a handle for the champion's spear; a hand-stick for the horse-boy; twigs for three spanceis; materials for hoops; materials for a chum-dash; the wild animals of each wood, through which there is a passage with necessity; the sea-wrack of each strand; the salt-leaf of each rock; the produce of each wave outside the rock; each wood which is without triple divisions; grinding upon the wheat-stone; an acknowledged fair-green; going into a boat; playing chess in the house of a chieftain; salt in the house of a 'brewy' [Briugu] the mountain which overtops all; a chain upon a captive; there being a space between him and the fetter.⁴⁹

Mac Néill drew attention to the phrase 'the salmon of every place' to declare that the members of the *túath* had enjoyed communal fishing rights.⁵⁰ In citing other passages from early Irish law, adding his own interpretation to texts in *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland*, Mac Néill felt that he had strengthened the case that private fisheries had not existed in early medieval Ireland. The case went on until the 1930s, ultimately resulting in success for the accused.⁵¹ The case was appealed and tried again in London, where it resulted in defeat for the poachers. There were other examples of fisheries cases in the first half of the twentieth century in which early Irish law was invoked, which it is not possible to go into here for reasons of space, but the

Erne Fisheries case was the first of its kind in the Irish Free State. There were also cases where medieval laws were invoked: in 1862, the medieval Welsh laws attributed to Hywel Dda were cited in a case over foreshore access on Anglesey,⁵² and, as late as 2017, the medieval Icelandic law code *Grágás* was cited in court proceedings.⁵³ In these instances, the idea of medieval Irish law acting as a form of alternative justice was a reality instead of an idea or something to strive for.

Conclusion

While Heather Laird did not see alternative legal spaces in nineteenth-century Ireland as being the direct descendants of medieval Irish law, commonly referred to as 'Brehon', there is no doubt that much of what consisted alternative law was inspired by this. Due to their scholarly nature, the six volumes of *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland*, published between 1867 and 1901 were not publicly accessible, nor were they of widespread influence, but, due to frequent news articles, people were aware of the existence of medieval Irish law; knew that, according to modern commentators, they may have been entitled to rights which were denied to them in their own time period; and due to the frequent recourses to laws and practices still in effect, may have upheld some of them. However, the most valuable aspect of medieval Irish law, was the idea of it and how it inspired people. As we have seen, many Nationalists in the late-nineteenth and early-twentieth centuries saw it as something to inspire a new system of law in an imagined future independent state or during the actual Free State. From the inception of the project to translate the laws in the 1850s, there was an awareness of the power that the laws might have, as was demonstrated by the inclusion of an anti-golden age narrative included in the application to the Government for funding, which indicates an awareness that the laws might have been used by Nationalists to subvert British rule in Ireland. Even if this was not entirely the intention, the law codes provoked a sense of pride in 'our national laws', which dated back to great antiquity and which were seen as fair and just, unlike the imported English common law. The laws in translation also allowed commentators to read the version of history they wished to into the texts, reflecting whatever political sentiments they might have had. The publication of *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland* meant that

early Irish law provided a sense of alternative justice, especially through their nineteenth-century translation.

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- 7 Letter Charles Graves to John O'Donovan, 4 August 1851, RIA 24 O 39/JOD/124.
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- 40 Laurence Ginnell, *The Brehon Laws* (London: T. F. Unwin, 1924), 130-1.
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- 43 *Ibid.*, vii.
- 44 'Lectures on Brehon Laws', *Irish Press* Thursday, 29 December 1932), 5.
- 45 The case is discussed in full in Thomas Mohr, 'Salmon of Knowledge', *Peritia* 16 (2002): 360-95 [= SK]. Unless otherwise stated, all of the following references are taken from this article.
- 46 SK, 363.
- 47 SK, 364-5.
- 48 SK, 365.
- 49 W. H. Hancock, T. O'Mahoney, A. G. Richey & R. Atkinson (ed), *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland*, V (Dublin: Her Majesty's Stationary Office, 1901), 505-6. *Andach* is not glossed in *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland*. O'Davoren's *Glossary* explains the word as meaning 'angry' or 'evil' (s.v. 'main-andach' in the *Glossary* in vol. VI of *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland*), yet this does not seem to make sense here. The *Dictionary of the Irish Language* entry suggests that it could also mean 'worthless', possibly making the phrase 'worthless produce of every water', *dil. le3470* 17 November 2022, and so could possibly refer to flotsam in the water. However, the key phrase discussed in this passage is *áé áite* and so we need not over-concern ourselves with the meaning of *andach* here.
- 50 SK, 366-7.
- 51 SK, 372.
- 52 See Huw Pryce and Gwilym Owen, 'Medieval Welsh Law and the Mid-Victorian Foreshore', *The Journal of Legal History*, 35.2 (2014): 172-199, for details.
- 53 See '13th century body of law used in case against MMA fighter', https://ceilandmonitor.mbl.is/news/news/2017/04/12/13th_century_body_of_law_used_in_case_against_mma_ff/, web 1 February 2021.

'Not justice exactly': Utopian Hopes of Fair Solutions in the Wars and at Home in Sebastian Barry's *Days Without End*

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Abstract: If one definition of justice is ceaseless individual responsibility for the victim of wars and violence, it is safe to say that injustice is the ceaseless shirking from such responsibility. In *Days Without End*, a novel of an Irishman involved in wars in nineteenth-century United States, Sebastian Barry is unsparing in his critique of such avoidance. His depiction of atrocities committed by whites against Native Americans leaves no doubt about the extent of that which he refers to as 'the sheer...brutality of it all'. The novel is grim, but funny and gentle, too – remarkably so in the light of the ground it covers. If, moreover, justice is a 'complex term for finding fair solutions to challenges in personal relations', then, indeed, the central characters in Barry's tale – Thomas McNulty, 'child of poor Sligoians', and John Cole, 'whose people were run out' of the American East long ago – find themselves enmeshed in questions of justice. They are professional soldiers, but they also, seemingly nurturing an unspoken – arguably utopian – hope, pursue possibilities of finding sustainable alternatives to conventional modes of being in society. My article explores how, driven by silent hopes of fair solutions in their lives, Thomas and John come to engage, not only in warfare, but in cross-dressing, adoption across ethnic boundaries, and same-sex marriage. In doing so, they attempt to resist the false and destructive boundaries by which individuals of certain ethnicity or sexual orientation are separated from mainstream society.

Keywords: Sligo, ethnicity, gay, diluvian, utopian, Native American, 'Indian', cross-dressing, insularity.